

Transformational Leadership and Attainment of Educational Objectives in Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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Abstract

This paper investigated the relationship between transformational leadership and the attainment of educational objectives in secondary schools in Rivers State. It adopted a descriptive survey. Four research questions and three null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study was carried out in secondary schools in Rivers State using the teachers. A questionnaire, Transformational Leadership and Attainment of Educational Objectives in Secondary Schools in Rivers State (TLAOSSRS), designed by the researchers were used to collect data for the study. The data collected from 150 teachers was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 23. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Pearson moment correlation coefficient was implored in testing the hypotheses. The findings revealed that transformative leadership ensures that an organization is turned around through participative interaction process and making the opinion of the subordinate to count. Transformative leadership influences the behaviour of followers through the use of people, the ability of the leader to change followers' attitudes, raise their commitment through interactive process with the followers to enhance the opportunity and chances of such an organization in terms of high productivity and safe working environment.

Keywords: attainment, educational objectives, transformational leadership, secondary school